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What determines technology transfer in Africa? Factors influencing technology imports from China to African economies

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Abstract

This research aims to elucidate the factors influencing technology transfer, conceptualized as the influx of high-technology imports. The research question posed is: What are the principal determinants that influence the volume of high-tech imports from China to African nations, and how reliable are the conventional gravity model variables when employed with various geographical measures within the context of Chinese high-tech exports to Africa? The study encompasses 53 African economies, categorized into five geographical regions. To examine the determinants of Chinese imports, we applied the trade gravity in levels using a panel data set spanning from 2016 to 2021. We employed the semi-mixed effect method using the Poisson pseudo-maximum likelihood estimator. The findings of the study reveal that non-traditional factors predominantly exert a significant impact on trade flows. While the majority of the variables behaved in accordance with expectations, some anomalies were also detected, which necessitate further consideration in policy formulation.

Keywords: Africa, China, technology transfer

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1. Introduction

The article is the result of the research project 'Digital Silk Road as a network of technological connections between China and Europe within value chains: towards win-win or decoupling?' financed by the National Service Centre, Poland. As the largest developing economy and the continent with the greatest number of developing countries, China and Africa maintain strong cooperation in the field of development. Increasingly, technology is highlighted as a critical area of collaboration in numerous meetings, summits, and China-Africa forums. Technology is a major bottleneck in African industrialization, and its transfer from China could partially alleviate these problems (Achuo et al., 2021; David and Grobler, 2020; He, 2013).

China's growing involvement in Africa has sparked a contentious debate, with some arguing that it drains Africa's manufacturing potential and resources without yielding substantial benefits,

thereby contributing to underdevelopment. Conversely, others perceive China as a development partner, beneficial to both parties (e.g. Mlambo et al., 2016; Broadman, 2017). Much of the research underscores a crucial transition in China's focus in Africa from infrastructure to technological areas, especially following the introduction of the Digital Silk Road (CIO, 2021; Hruby, 2021). The technological facet of this relationship, central to our study, reflects both the advantages and challenges of China's involvement (Habyarimana & Opoku, 2018; Tugendhat, 2021), and highlights the historical progression and potential of technology transfer (Gravett, 2023; Li, 2016). China's pivotal role in molding Africa's technological and economic future is visible in trade and investment patterns. Moreover, China's expanding technological influence in Africa is a critical factor shaping the continent and its economy.

The study focuses on trade, as it is a significant conduit for technology transfer, especially in the context of the surveyed countries with low innovation levels (UN Economic Commission for Africa, 2023; Eaton and Kortum, 1999). This channel is more developed than FDI, acquiring IPRs such as technical know-how, patent and license agreements, and migrations of human capital in African economies.

In this context, technology transfer is one of the less explored topics in studies examining the relations between Africa and China. Two contrasting viewpoints emerge in the discourse. On the one hand, some authors argue that the opening of Africa to trade with China is not reflected in the transfer of technology to African countries¹ (Patroba, 2012; Elu and Price, 2010; Youngman, 2013). On the other hand, the positive impact of the import of capital goods from China to Africa is indicated, as technology transfer takes place simultaneously with it (Munemo, 2013). The authors often pointed to various internal or external factors that influence the potential for technology transfer (Borojo & Jiang, 2016).

The high-tech goods imported by African countries are not homogeneous, which prompted this study to examine two distinct categories of such goods separately. This approach aims to contribute to the scientific knowledge on the role of different factors influencing the import of two different types of high-tech goods from China to African countries. To the authors' knowledge, no prior study has addressed the determinants of China's technology exports to Africa while taking into account the heterogeneity of the import streams. Furthermore, no study has analyzed all African countries, further divided into 5 geographical groups. This also made it possible to indicate whether identical factors attracting technology from China embodied in the two high-tech import streams are at play within each group. On a broader scale, the analysis may suggest some changes in the foreign policy of African economies (e.g. a nation's stance on trade relations with China, and the role of FDI related to high-tech imports, areas of technological trade cooperation to be developed or reduced due to dependency, etc.).

The study's objective is to investigate the determinants of technology transfer, defined as the flow of high-technology imports. In research, FDI or R&D and other variables related to technological inputs are often assumed as proxies for technology transfer. However, it is difficult to find detailed data for all African countries. Therefore, it is possible that the authors' alternative approach prove useful in identifying technology transfer factors when data availability is limited. High-tech goods are divided into two categories, based on Lall's classification: high technology manufactures (electronic and electrical) and technology manufactures (other). This classification is intentional, as the categories represent heterogeneous groups (Lall, 2000). Moreover, China is the global leader in the export of goods within the first category, while in the second category, it still has a small share in the world².

We posed the following research question: what are the key determinants influencing the volume of high-tech imports from China to African countries, and how robust are the traditional gravity

1. The research will be discussed in more detail in the "Literature review".

2. For a more detailed discussion of the categories, see "Construction of variables".

model variables when applied to different geographical measures in the context of Chinese high-tech exports to Africa?

The subject of the study are 53 African economies, grouped into 5 regions based on geographical location, following the "Geographic Regions" classification by the United Nations Statistics Division (United Nations Statistics Division, 2022). To investigate the determinants of the Chinese imports with the use of the trade gravity in levels approach in a panel data set covering the period 2016–2021, we have applied the semi-mixed effect method using Poisson pseudo-maximum likelihood (PPML) estimator as suggested by the recent empirical literature. The selection of the research period was driven by two factors. First, the year 2016 marks the introduction of the Digital Silk Road and an intensification of economic relations between China and Africa. Second, 2021 was chosen as the endpoint due to data availability for several countries.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, no previous studies have explored the trade relationship between Africa and China in technological goods with such depth. By recognizing the heterogeneity of technology imports and incorporating unconventional variables and clusters in the modeling, this study provides a more accurate depiction of the underlying relationships than previous literature. This allows the foundations to be laid for a better development of technology-related policies in African economies.

The theoretical contribution of this study is multifaceted. First, it expands the discourse on international relations by providing a detailed analysis of the factors of technology transfer, focusing mainly on the interactions between China and African nations. Second, the study contributes to ongoing discussions on developing countries' technology policies. The study identifies the impact of various factors on the intensity of technology transfer through the import of different types of technological goods. It enriches the discourse of technology transfer research by approaching it as a heterogeneous process.

The study's findings also have practical implications. The insights gathered can help economies at varying stages of development, aiding them in understanding the intricacies and capitalizing on the prospects brought about by the ongoing changes in worldwide technology and power dynamics. It also gives an indication of how technological strategies should differ according to regions and types of technology.

The article consists of three parts, introduction, and conclusion. The first section reviews the relevant literature. The second section describes data and methods, as well as characterizes the discussed groups of African economies. The third section presents the results and discussion. The conclusions address the research questions, the purpose of the analysis and its limitations.

2. Literature review

The literature highlights a lack of comprehensive studies on trade links between China and all African countries, particularly in relation to Africa's technological advancement. In order to construct the most accurate model of the impact of trade with China on technology transfer to Africa, several selection criteria were used. First, the focus was on articles published within the last 15 years. Furthermore, an important criterion for the selection of articles was their citation according to popular websites, e.g. Mendeley or Semantic Scholar.

The literature review was conducted through two approaches. The first group of papers indicated the use of gravity models in relation to trade relations between China and Africa. On the basis of the selected papers, an attempt was made to select the variables used in the model constructed by the authors. The approaches to the construction of a gravity model proposed in these studies were also compared.

The second group of studies focused on the research regarding the impact of overall foreign trade on technological progress and technology transfer in Africa. In this group, the use of a gravity model was not a selection criterion; however, the inclusion of panel data analysis was considered

important. The collected papers made it possible to supplement the model with variables affecting technological progress in the surveyed countries.

2.1 Chinese-African trade in gravity models

Gravity models have gained widespread popularity in the scientific literature and seem to be appropriate for studying trade relations between countries for several reasons³. First, by incorporating economic size and distance, they are an effective framework for understanding and predicting trade relationships between countries. Second, these models are particularly valuable for policy researchers, as they allow for the estimation of the trade impacts of various trade-related policies, ranging from traditional tariffs to new "behind-the-border" measures. Third, in the context of trade facilitation, the knowledge and application of gravity models are substantial. They can help understand how trade facilitation influences trade, making them a valuable tool in trade policy analysis (Shahriar et al. 2019; De Benedictis and Taglioni, 2011).

These reasons make gravity models a suitable choice for studying trade relations between China and Africa. They provide a comprehensive and empirically robust framework for analyzing and predicting international trade patterns.

Many of studies applying gravity models utilize conventional variables, e.g. Wang et al. (2024), Fu and Eguegu (2021) or Yang (2023). However, there are also some studies that apply additional, non-conventional variables into the gravity models for trade between Africa and China. Research from the last two decades is detailed in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Non-conventional variables applied by gravity models

Author	Variables	Limitations of approach
De Grauwe, et al. (2012)	Distance Landlocked GDP per capita Colony Resource Governance Language	Many binary variables; limited number of trade partners
Akowuah et al. (2020)	Distance Population Relative factor endowment (GDP gap) Inflation	Limited number of African economies; omitting some important variables
Johnston, et al. (2015)	GDP Distance Population Real exchange rate Landlocked Island Language Common boarder Market economy status	Short period of research; geographic variables have too high a share in the selection of exogenous variables
Gold and Rasiah (2022)	GDP Population Distance Trade openness	Some of evidences were ambiguous; limited number of countries; significant reliance on geography-related variables

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3. However, there are some limitations of gravity models. There is theoretical inconsistency in these models. The basic version of these models omits many important variables that impact trade. There are also some problems with endogeneity. Moreover, classical gravity models are not dynamic, do not take into account the economy's preferences and do not cover network effects when there are more economies.

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Author	Variable	Limitations of approach
	Oil/minerals dependence Share of agriculture and manufacturing Political stability Corruption Land area Landlocked	
Hu and van Marrewijk (2013)	GDP per capita Distance Colonial Ties Language Legal Currency Union RTA Common Border Landlocked	Some traditional variables did not operate; limited number of economies; political variables have too high a share in the selection of exogenous variables
Miao et al. (2020)	GDP per capita Physical capital Inflation FDI Inflation FDI Health expenditure Institutional quality	Limited number of economies
Didier and Hoarau (2021)	Distance Contiguity Language Resources Income inequality Terms of trade Corruption Government effectiveness Regulatory quality Rule of law Political stability Democracy WTO	Some of variables are similar, especially in the institutional dimension; significant reliance on institution-related variables; underestimation of the country welfare variables
Guan and Sheong (2020)	Real GDP Population Distance Real exchange rate Number of trade agreements Island Recession	Short period of analysis; significant reliance on geography-related variables; lack of variables reflecting broader institutions
Alemu and Zhang (2019)	GDP Distance Population Exchange rate Openness Resources (oil and ores and metal)	Limited number of variables; lack of variables reflecting broader institutions
Wang et al. (2024)	GDP and GDP per capita Distance Terms of trade FDI Population growth	Short duration of BRI; significant reliance on variables related to the openness of the economy; lack of variables reflecting broader institutions

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Author	Variable	Limitations of approach
	Exchange rate Belt and Road Initiative member	
Guan et al. (2021)	GDP Distance Population FDI Exchange rate	Very limited number of variables; concentration on the specific area
Bekele and Mersha (2019)	Coffee exports GDP Weighted distance Population Real exchange rate Openness	Very limited number of variables; limited number of economies; concentration on the specific activity
Chen et al. (2022)	GDP Population Infrastructure Institutional quality Forest resources	Very limited number of variables; concentration on the specific area and specific activity

Source: Own elaboration.

2.2 Foreign trade on technological progress in Africa

The concept that importing goods can stimulate productivity growth, and consequently, economic growth is rooted in early trade models developed by Ethier (1982) and Markusen (1989). The endogenous growth theory, as discussed by Sachs et al. (1995), views the global exchange of innovation and advanced technology as a key factor influencing long-term economic growth. This is particularly significant for countries that lack their own capabilities, such as developing economies. The 'catch-up' growth theory (Boersma, B., and Wit, 1997) suggests that technology diffusion should be faster when the technological gap between developing and developed economies is larger. While many authors have provided studies supporting this (e.g. Asada, 2022), this relation has not always been clear-cut (Sahoo and Dash, 2022).

This leads to the conclusion that foreign trade could be a significant conduit for the dissemination of technological progress among economies, with foreign innovations and technologies being integrated into the inflow of capital goods, intermediate products, and final goods and services. This concept is reflected in this manuscript. For example, Keller (2021) and Cai and Xiang (2022), have formulated the concept of technology transmission and demonstrated the linkages between productivity and growth and international trade. Sujová et al. (2021) demonstrated that trade openness enhances the diffusion of innovation. Furthermore, Zhang et al. (2022) analyzed the impact of technological progress and trade in digital technology on China's regional development.

In terms of economic development and technological progress, various factors should be considered (Koo and Pekins, 2016). For example, Akcigit and Kerr (2018) highlighted key determinants that shape the relationship between innovation and trade. Although numerous studies suggest that developing countries may be reducing the technology gap by importing goods, this does not always lead to productivity or economic growth. Feng et al. (2016) argued that technology-driven product upgrading helped Chinese companies enhance their presence in export markets, a finding supported by Castellani and Fassio (2019) for Swedish companies. However, ineffective state policies and knowledge accumulation are major obstacles in adopting advanced technology (Koo and Perkins, 2016; Lo and Cissokho, 2023). Venturini (2015) found that a low degree of industry specialization in ICT cannot be compensated by trade openness. Ohnsorge and Quaglietti (2023) showed that increasing trade costs might harm economic development. Luqman and Murtaza (2023) argued that

imported inputs have positive effects on companies' productivity in selected South Asian economies. Lastly, Akcigit and Melitz (2022) connected trade and innovation in an econometric model.

An increasing number of scientific studies are being published that demonstrate how constraints on foreign trade, such as decoupling, impede technological development (e.g., Witt et al, 2021; Pesce, 2014; Elu and Price, 2010). In response, Hsieh et al. (2023) formulated a two-country model of trade and creative destruction, involving both domestic and foreign firms. They demonstrated the influence of foreign trade on a company's innovativeness, depending on the type of activity. Similar findings are reported by Perla et al. (2021). Coelli et al. (2022) quantified the positive effect of expanded market access on innovation due to trade liberalization, while Aghion et al. (2024) and Impullitti et al. (2022) extended this effect to the firm level.

Several studies have showed the impact of technology on foreign trade. Some examples are presented below.

Abedin and Duan (2022) found that the digital economy, when combined with trade, positively impacts Africa's economic growth. Ajakaiye and Page (2012) identified technology and trade as key determinants of African industrialization. UNCTAD (2023) emphasized the importance of developing resilient and advanced global value chains in Africa. Borojo and Jiang (2016) demonstrated that Africa's trade openness positively impacts GDP growth and TFP when combined with institutional quality and human capital. Munemo (2013) argued that Chinese capital goods are crucial for technology transfer in Africa. Duodu et al. (2024) argued that Chinese trade significantly influences African economies with strong institutions. He (2013) showed that Chinese imports have a more substantial positive effect on economic development in Sub-Saharan Africa compared to imports from the US and France. Rojo (2024) revealed China's significant and growing presence in technological diffusion across Africa. Hou et al. (2022) found that trade with China offers more opportunities for Ghanaian companies to increase productivity. Patroba (2012) and Youngman (2013) showed that trade with China does not necessarily lead to technology transfer in Kenya and Botswana, respectively. Okafor (2021) argued that the use of imported intermediates moderates the productivity effects of export market destinations, while Dahmani et al. (2022) and Alani et al. (2023) found that trade openness positively impacts economic development in Tunisia and Uganda, respectively.

To sum up, the above mentioned literature underscores the significance of technology import and its influence on economic expansion and efficiency. However, none of the researches address the issue of what influences the quantity of foreign technology imports, hence our study concentrates on an empirically uninvestigated area. We scrutinize the factor that initiates discussions about technology transfer – the factors that attract different types of technology to a country. Therefore, this article expands the research of Wang et al. (2024) by examining African economies and their relations with China. Our approach aligns with Akowuah et al. (2020), Miao et al. (2020), Hu and van Marrewijk (2013), and De Grauwe et al. (2012), who also included additional variables and examined a large number of African economies. However, our study is distinctive in its detailed analysis of trade in specific categories of technological goods. We also reference Gold and Rasiah (2022) and Alemu and Zhang (2019) to highlight that trade relations between China and Africa extend beyond exporting resources and importing low-processed goods.

3. Data and methods

3.1 Data

This study uses several data sources that provide data on trade between African countries and selected macroeconomic categories. The first source is the UNCTAD, which offers data on foreign trade (including high technology products), GDP, FORCE and OUTPUT. The second source is the World Bank that contains RES. The last one are the websites OpenStreetMap (2024) and Distance Calculator (2024) with a calculator that was used to determine the distance between the capitals of the countries.

The study examines nearly all African countries that trade with China and for which data is available. The countries are divided into 5 groups/regions (Northern Africa NA, Western Africa WA, Central Africa CA, Eastern Africa EA, and Southern Africa SA) based on "Geographic Regions" as defined by the United Nations Statistics Division (UNCTAD, 2022; Table 2). A total of 53 countries were included in the study (two countries, Saint Helena, and Sudan, were excluded from the analysis due to lack of data). The analysis period covers annual data from 2016–2021.

Table 2. Classification of African economies

Group NA	Group EA	Group CA	Group SA	Group WA
Algeria	Burundi	Angola	Botswana	Benin
Egypt	Comoros	Cameroon	Eswatini	Burkina Faso
Libya	Djibouti	Central African Republic	Lesotho	Cabo Verde
Morocco	Eritrea	Chad	Namibia	Côte d'Ivoire
Tunisia	Ethiopia	Congo	South Africa	Gambia
	Kenya	Congo, Dem. Rep.		Ghana
	Madagascar	Equatorial Guinea		Guinea
	Malawi	Gabon		Guinea-Bissau
	Mauritius	Sao Tome and Principe		Liberia
	Mozambique			Mali
	Rwanda			Mauritania
	Seychelles			Niger
	Somalia			Nigeria
	South Sudan			Senegal
	Tanzania			Sierra Leone
	Uganda			Togo
	Zambia			
	Zimbabwe			

Source: UNCTAD (2022).

Group NA in the analysis includes 5 countries. Following the wave of the Arab Spring in 2011, the region is characterized by a rather unstable political and economic environment and a low level of security⁴. In terms of the most important macroeconomic and demographic indicators, North Africa should be considered a relatively well-developed part of the African continent (3 out of 5 countries are in the 10% of economies with the highest GDP). The largest market by population is Egypt (it is in the top 10% in Africa, and it is the second largest economy on the continent). The area as a whole has the highest average GDP in current prices among the surveyed groups, but also a significant standard deviation, which indicates the diversification of GDP. It should be emphasized that all countries in the area have access to the sea, but differ in the use of raw materials in generating GDP. In terms of mean of total natural resources rents as percent of GDP⁵ this group is second only to group CA. Libya is among the economies with the highest rate discussed (not only in Africa, but also in the world). Group NA countries are characterized by low dependence on trade with China in general (the lowest mean in exports and second to last in imports; group SA was only worse). These countries are not important high-tech producers either in Africa or in the world⁶.

4. Low horizontal Political Stability Index, Economic Freedom Index and Corruption Perceptions Index. They rank better in terms of HDI, as all countries are in the high HDI group (Algeria ranks highest).

5. Total natural resources rents are the sum of oil rents, natural gas rents, coal rents (hard and soft), mineral rents, and forest rents (World Bank, 2023).

6. In terms of innovation indicators (e.g. GII), Morocco and Egypt rank highest (Johnson Cornell University, INSEAD,

Most of the countries in this group are in the top 10% of economies importing the most high-tech products from the world, with the exception of Libya and Tunisia, in selected years. Moreover, apart from these two countries, the others are characterized by high imports of high-tech products from China in absolute terms (they are in the top 10% in Africa). However, the trade relations in the area of high-tech remain more developed with Europe than with China (especially in terms of imports⁷). This is evidenced by the low share of imports of high-tech products from China in relation to the world or GDP. The exceptions are Tunisia, and to a lesser extent Morocco, which are in the first decile in Africa in this respect. In addition, Morocco has the largest total import of high-tech products⁸ after Egypt. Imports of electronics from China are of particular importance for Tunisia and Morocco. Algeria⁹ ranks worst in terms of the share of Chinese high-tech imports. All countries in this area have signed a MoU with China under the BRI, which boosts trade and inflows of Chinese investments¹⁰. Trade between China and Northern Africa has increased dramatically since the beginning of 21st century, but it has largely reproduced patterns of unequal trade. China has promised to increase investments in high-value-added industries and to strengthen cooperation in science and technology with countries across Northern Africa.

Group EA in the analysis includes 18 economies. Countries are quite diverse in terms of GDP, growth dynamics or level of socio-economic development (Cieřlik, 2016; Cieřlik et al., 2020)¹¹. The largest markets in the region are Ethiopia and Tanzania (in terms of population; they are in the top 10% in Africa). Kenya has the highest GDP. In general, in terms of the most important macroeconomic and demographic indicators, the region should be considered an underdeveloped part of the African continent (none of the countries was included in the top 10% of economies with the highest GDP in Africa). The area as a whole has the lowest mean of GDP in current prices among the surveyed groups and the lowest standard deviation, which indicates a slight variation in GDP between countries. It should be emphasized that not all countries in the area have access to the sea and use raw materials to generate GDP with varying intensity. In terms of mean of total natural resources rents as percent of GDP, this group occupies the last but one place (Southern Africa ranks only worse), but the differentiation in this respect is clear. Group EA countries are characterized by a fairly high dependence on imports from China in general (a higher mean was observed only in group WA) and a significant dependence on exports to the Chinese market (only CA had a higher mean)¹². These countries are not important high-tech producers either in Africa or in the world¹³. They also do not import a lot of high-tech products from the world and China. This is evidenced by the low share of imports of high-tech products from China in relation to the world or GDP. The exceptions are Djibouti and Mauritius, which are in the first decile in Africa in this respect. In absolute terms, the exceptions are Ethiopia and Kenya, which are in the top 10% of

WIPO, 2022).

7. Exports are much lower and focused on Europe. Intra-industry trade is practically non-existent (UNCTAD, 2022).

8. For example, Huawei provides communication technology for Morocco's national railway system, has constructed a logistics center at Tangier Med Port, and was involved in building and launching the Marrakesh Safe City project.

9. That is, Chinese FDI going to Algeria bypass sectors that require advanced technologies, which can be imported from China.

10. Although it should be noted that they are distributed very unevenly. By mid-2022, Algeria and Egypt received the most Chinese investments (respectively 48% and 44% of all FDI flowing into the 5 surveyed economies), while only 0.2% of these investments went to Tunisia. The situation with foreign trade is similar – Algeria and Egypt dominate, and to a lesser extent Morocco (World Bank, 2023) (American Enterprise Institute and Heritage Foundation, 2022).

11. For example, in the HDI, countries in the region except Mauritius (very high HDI) and the Seychelles (high HDI) are below the world average. South Sudan ranks lowest (low HDI). Several Group EA countries rank among the worst in the world for Poverty headcount ratio at country poverty lines (% of population): South Sudan, Madagascar and Eritrea (World Bank, 2023) (UNDP, 2022).

12. However, one should be aware of the high standard deviation. For example, the largest share of imports to China in total was held by e.g. Ethiopia and Kenya, while in terms of exports, the highest rates were in Eritrea and South Sudan, while some countries had rates close to 0.

13. In terms of innovation indicators (e.g. GII) they are rated very low (Johnson Cornell University, INSEAD, WIPO, 2022).

importers of high-tech products from China in Africa. High-tech trade relations of the area remain, unlike group NA, more developed with China than with Europe (especially in terms of import; a large gap in imports in favor of China can be found in Djibouti, Kenya, Mozambique, Tanzania, or Uganda). Almost all economies of the area (except Mauritius) have signed a MoU with China under the BRI¹⁴, which should theoretically boost trade and investment inflows from China¹⁵. Economic cooperation between China and the region is extensive. Countries from this region are also the main beneficiaries of Chinese loans in Africa (mainly Ethiopia, Zambia, Kenya). China has been playing a prominent role in infrastructure developments in the region, with its enablement of Chinese construction companies to put their expertise to test and gain access to new markets, while at the same time helping the region reduce its staggering infrastructure deficit. In terms of the technology sector, China has made several important investments in East Africa (mainly ZTE, Huawei, China Mobile, China Telecom). Moreover, factories producing advanced products are being built (e.g. in Tanzania or Uganda). China (mainly through Huawei) cooperates with national governments in the construction of telecommunications infrastructure, e.g. in Tanzania's National ICT Broadband Phase II and III, Kenya's National optic Fiber backbone Infrastructure, Phase II, Ethiopian Telecom Transformation and Expansion (4G network and mobile expansion) – 7 and 6 Circles.

Group CA in the analysis covers 9 economies. The countries, similarly to group EA, are diverse in many socio-economic aspects¹⁶. The largest market in the region is the DRC (in terms of population), which is one of the largest in Africa. Angola, on the other hand, has the highest GDP. In general, in terms of the main macroeconomic and demographic indicators, Central Africa should be considered a very underdeveloped part of the African continent (only Angola was in the 10% of economies with the highest GDP in Africa in 2017). The area as a whole is characterized by the second lowest mean of GDP in current prices and low standard deviation, after group EA, which indicates a slight variation in production between countries. It should be emphasized that not all countries have access to the sea. However, they all use raw materials to generate GDP with considerable intensity. In terms of mean of total natural resources rents as percent of GDP, this group ranks first in the five surveyed groups, but the differentiation in this respect is clear. Group CA countries are characterized by a moderate dependence on imports from China in general and the greatest dependence on exports to the Chinese market among the surveyed groups¹⁷. These countries are not important high-tech producers either in Africa or in the world¹⁸. They do not import a lot of high-tech products from the world and China. This is evidenced by the low share of imports of high-tech products from China in relation to the world or GDP. The trade relations in the area of a high-tech remain, as in group NA, more developed with Europe than with China (especially in terms of import, with the exception of the DRC, which imports slightly more high-tech equipment from China than from Europe). Almost all of the area's economies (apart from the Central African Republic and Sao Tome and Principe) have signed MoUs with China under the BRI, which encourages trade and capital inflows from China¹⁹. Economic cooperation between China and

14. There is no official information about the Comoros.

15. Ethiopia, Kenya, and Tanzania account for 58% of imports from China, while Comoros – 0.2%. Zambia accounts for over half of the region's exports to China. In terms of Chinese FDI, Ethiopia and Zambia receive the most (22% and 15% of all group EA recipients, respectively) (UNCTAD, 2022) (American Enterprise Institute and Heritage Foundation, 2022)

16. For example, in HDI countries of the region are in medium HDI and low HDI. Chad and the Central African Republic rank among the worst countries in the world in terms of HDI. However, in view of the poverty headcount ratio at country poverty lines (% of population), most of the countries from group CA are in the infamous world forefront (World Bank, 2023).

17. Angola and the DRC mainly export raw materials to China (UNCTAD, 2022).

18. In terms of innovation indicators (e.g. GII), they are rated very low (Johnson Cornell University, INSEAD, WIPO, 2022).

19. It is difficult to unequivocally confirm whether the DRC joined the BRI. The DRC and Angola account for 64% of imports from China, while Sao Tome and Principe – 0.2%. Angola accounts for half of the region's exports to China, and the DRC – 27%. The rest of the countries do not play a significant role. In the case of Chinese FDI, most of them go to Angola

the region is extensive. Angola is the largest beneficiary of Chinese loans in Africa. The region cooperates with China in the field of less advanced technologies. Investments are focused on mining and processing industries. There has been no investment in technology so far. Although China is the main supplier of high-tech products to the region, the value of these imports is still small. Certain areas of cooperation between China and the region in the field of technology can be identified. An example is the National Broadband Network Phase I and II: 4G Mobile Broadband (LTE) or South Atlantic Inter Link created by Huawei in cooperation with the Cameroonian government.

Group SA in the analysis includes 5 economies. The countries of the region are highly differentiated in many socio-economic aspects²⁰. In terms of the most important macroeconomic and demographic indicators, South Africa should be considered a relatively well-developed part of the continent, but with very large inequalities. This image of the region is mainly due to South Africa, which is the region's largest market (in terms of population) and the biggest economy in terms of GDP and inequality (the country with the highest Gini coefficient in the world, 3rd economy in Africa). The area as a whole is characterized by the second highest mean of GDP in current prices, after group NA, and the highest standard deviation of all groups, which confirms the large development gap between South Africa and the rest of the region. Not all countries in the area have access to the sea. They use raw materials to generate GDP with a similar and low intensity (the least in Botswana). In terms of mean of total natural resources rents as percent of GDP, this group ranks last among the five surveyed. Group SA countries are characterized by the lowest of all group's dependence on imports from China in general and the second lowest (after group WA) dependence on exports to the Chinese market. South Africa is a major high-tech producer in Africa²¹. It imports a lot of high-tech products from the world and China. This is evidenced by the high share of imports of high-tech products from China in relation to the world or the GDP of the discussed group of economies. Other countries in the region play a marginal role in trade relations with China in the field of high-tech products. The trade relations in the area of high-tech remain much more developed with Europe than with China. China's cooperation with the region in terms of technology is extensive only with South Africa, where China is investing in this sector. Other countries have a marginal share in these relations. Almost all of the area's economies (except Eswatini) have signed a MoU with China under the BRI, which encourages trade and capital inflows from China²².

Group WA in the analysis includes 16 economies. In terms of the most important macroeconomic and demographic indicators, West Africa should be considered a very unevenly developed part of the continent with clear signs of economic backwardness. Many countries in the region are among the poorest in the world²³. The largest market in the region (in terms of population) and the largest economy in terms of GDP is Nigeria (the largest economy in Africa). The area as a whole has the third highest mean of GDP in current prices and the second highest of all standard deviation groups, which confirms the large development gap between countries. Not all countries in the area have access to the sea. They use raw materials in generating GDP with medium intensity (Liberia is the strongest). In terms of mean of total natural resources rents as percent of GDP, this group ranks third out of five surveyed. Group WA countries are characterized by the highest dependence of all groups

and the DRC (29% and 24% of all group CA, respectively). (UNCTAD, 2022; The American Enterprise Institute and The Heritage Foundation, 2022).

20. South Africa is in high HDI, Botswana and Namibia in medium HDI, and Lesotho and Eswatini in low HDI. In view of the poverty headcount ratio at country poverty lines (% of population), apart from Botswana and Namibia, the other countries are characterized by high values (over 50%). South Africa performs well compared to the region in terms of production-related indicators (e.g. competitiveness). However, in rankings showing the business climate, e.g. in terms of corruption or stability, Botswana and Namibia are better than South Africa (Index of Economic Freedom, 2022) (World Bank, 2023).

21. In terms of innovation indicators (e.g. GII), the countries of the region, apart from South Africa, are rated low.

22. South Africa carries out 95% of the region's trade with China. The same is true for Chinese FDI, 74% of which have been attracted to South Africa (UNCTAD, 2022; The American Enterprise Institute and The Heritage Foundation, 2022).

23. In terms of the HDI, all countries, except Gambia and Cabo Verde, are in the low HDI group. Niger ranks lowest. Several countries in the group are among the worst in the world in terms of poverty headcount ratio at country poverty lines (% of population) (World Bank, 2023).

on imports from China in total and the third smallest dependence on exports to the Chinese market. None of the countries is a major high-tech producer in Africa or in the world²⁴. The region does not import a lot of high-tech products from the world and China. This is evidenced by the low share of imports of high-tech products from China in relation to the world or GDP. However, the trade relations in the area of high-tech remain somewhat more developed with China than with Europe, although Europe dominates overall trade. Niger, Sierra Leone, and Guinea are most heavily dependent on imports of Chinese high-tech products. Almost all economies of the area (except Burkina Faso²⁵) have signed MoUs with China under the BRI, which encourages trade and capital inflows from China²⁶. China's cooperation with the region in terms of technology is extensive with selected countries. It has invested in the tech sector in Ghana and Nigeria. It also cooperates with the governments of the countries of the region in order to build technological infrastructure²⁷.

3.2 Construction of variables

The intensity of digital technology exchange from China to African countries is measured using two alternative dependent variables: the flow of high technology manufactures: electronic and electronic (MTCE) as well as flow of high technology manufactures: other (MTCO).

The variable MTCE stands for the flow of high-technology manufactures: electronic and electrical from China to African country. This category includes the most popular electrical and electronic office devices machines, automatic data processing machines or telecommunications equipment. These products are among China's flagship exports to world markets, especially developing countries²⁸. The variable MTCO denotes the flow of high-technology manufactures: other, which include more specialized technological products, such as aircraft, pharmaceuticals, or more complex specialized equipment. This type of products is much produced less frequently in China, as reflected in the incomparably lower export values of these products²⁹. Although China has specialized in high technology manufactures: electronic and electrical, it is no longer a major high technology manufacturer in the world manufactures: other. A detailed breakdown of the main categories and their subcategories is presented in UNCTAD (2022). Moreover, African countries are not yet technologically advanced enough to import more high-tech categories manufactures: other. Currently, there is a much greater demand for typical high technology manufactures: electronic and electrical.

The basic explanatory variables include the size of partner as measured by the log of Gross Domestic Product (logGDP) and the log of the distance between trade partners (log DIST). The distance is measured as the distance between the capitals of trade partners from African countries and China. These are classic variables used in a gravity trade model. To control the effect of capital labour and capital productivity, we use the following variables: total employment in all activities in thousand (in USD millions) and output per capita (in USD). We also included the ratio of natural

24. In terms of innovation indicators (e.g. GII), the countries of the region are rated low. Cape Verde ranks the highest (Johnson Cornell University, INSEAD, WIPO, 2022).

25. There is no clear information whether Niger and Benin have also signed the relevant agreements.

26. In terms of exports to China, Nigeria, Ghana, Guinea, and Mauritania perform respectively: 26%, 21%, 19% and 17%. Other countries do not play a major role. Imports from China were dominated by Nigeria – 55%. In the case of Chinese FDI in the region, 40% is received by Nigeria. A lot also goes to Ghana, Senegal, or Niger (UNCTAD, 2022; The American Enterprise Institute and The Heritage Foundation, 2022).

27. For example, it introduces the Galaxy Backbone Project for National Security Development System, or National Information Communication Technology Infrastructure Backbone, Phase I and II in Nigeria, Abidjan Video Surveillance Platform in Ivory Coast, and Fiber Optic Backbone Network Phase II in Sierra Leone.

28. In 2021, Chinese exports of these products accounted for 35% of global exports, and 34% of exports to developing countries, making them a leader in this type of production. In comparison, Europe accounted for 14% and 5.5% of such exports, respectively (UNCTAD, 2022).

29. In 2021, Chinese exports of these products accounted for 7% of global exports, and 13% of exports to developing markets. For comparison, Europe was responsible for 60% and 41% of such exports, respectively, i.e. it was the leader in the export of this type of products (UNCTAD, 2022).

resources to GDP of African countries (RES) as an indicator: total natural resources rents (% of GDP) (Table 3).

Table 3. Explanatory variables

Type of variable	Symbol	Full name	Explanation	Authors	Source
Traditional variables	GDP	GDP	Total GDP	Anggita (2015) Porojan (2001)	UNCTAD (2022)
	DIST	Distance	Distance between the capitals of related economies	Brun et al.(2005) De Benedictis and Taglioni (2011)	Distance Calculator (2023); ©OpenStreetMap
Alternative traditional variables	RFL	Development gap	Difference between GDP of pair of economies	Brodzicki and Śledzecka (2016) Helpman and Krugman (1985)	World Bank (2023)
	SEA	Landlock	Access to the sea.	Gold and Rasiah (2022) Hu and van Marrewijk (2013)	UNCTAD (2022)
Non-traditional variables	FORCE	Labour force	Total employment in all activities (in thousand)	Baier and Standaert (2020) Batra (2006)	UNCTAD (2022)
	PROD	Productivity	Total output (in USD millions)/ total employment in all activities (in thousand)	Baier and Standaert (2020) Christie (2002)	UNCTAD (2022)
	RES	Natural resources	Total natural resources rents (% of GDP)	Khosia (2015) Natale et al. (2015)	World Bank (2023)

Source: own compilation.

African countries differ in their level of wealth, which may affect the extent of trade with China. In connection with the above, it was assumed that the greater the differences in the level of development between countries, as measured by GDP, the lower the intensity of trade between them. To quantify this development gap, the difference between GDP per capita for individual pairs of countries (GDP_{pc} for countries i and j in period t) was determined according to the formula:

$$RLF_{ijt} = \ln|GDP_{pc_{jt}} - GDP_{pc_{it}}| \quad (1)$$

We furthermore apply a number of dummy variables to identify the geographical grouping of countries, resulting in 5 dummy variables (for $i = NA, EA, CA, SA$ or WA). The empirical studies proved that that the previous notion – the greater the difference in development between a given African country and China, the greater the tendency to import high-technology manufactures: electronic and electrical from China – is no longer valid. In the new model, the differences in GDP behave in accordance with the theorems (Helpman and Krugman, 1985), i.e. the smaller the differences in the level of economic development (measured, for example, by GDP), the more intensive the import of technology.

3.3 Methods

The gravity trade is considered one of the most important tools in trade analysis. It enables to determine and predict actual trade flows. The model has been known for 60 years – it was first presented in 1962 by Jan Tinbergen. Over time, the model has been developed quite intensively and currently has many empirical specifications/modifications.

With the growing body of empirical research utilizing the gravity model, there have been many considerations regarding the correctness of the selection of its estimation method, depending on the model's specification, both due to its analytical form and variable inclusion in the model. The basic assumption adopted in the model is that trade flows between two countries are proportional to their GDP and inversely proportional to the distance between them (Tinbergen, 1962). However, due

to its natural limitations, this assumption seems to be insufficient. This is one of the reasons why additional variables representing the specific features of both partner countries have been included in the model (Westerlund and Wilhelmsson, 2011).

The stochastic version of the panel data gravity equation has the following form:

$$T_{ijt} = \alpha_0 Y_{it}^{\beta_1} Y_{jt}^{\beta_2} Z_{ij}^{\gamma} X_{ijt}^{\alpha} e^{\delta D_{ij} + \nu_t + \eta_{ij}} \epsilon_{ijt} \quad (2)$$

where ν_t are time effects which could account for business cycles, η_{ij} are unobserved heterogeneity effects, and ϵ_{it} is the stochastic error term. Further, α_0 , β_1 , β_2 , γ , α , δ are unknown coefficients. It is worth noting that within the panel data, it is possible to include unobserved individual effects (i), time effects (t), as well as effects for pairs of countries (i,j). All of these effects can be treated as constant or random.

In the classic approach, the model (2) is transformed into a log-linear form and then estimated using OLS. In this estimation method, it is necessary to fulfill the assumption of independence of the explanatory variables of the model and the random component (homoscedasticity). Failure to meet this assumption results in the OLS estimation being inconsistent and biased (Santos Silva & Tenreyro, 2006). The proposed extension of the initial model to the form of additional explanatory variables may potentially generate a risk of heteroscedasticity.

The second problem with logarithmic transformations is the occurrence of zero or very low trade flows and, consequently, impossibility to calculate the logarithm value and perform the transformations mentioned³⁰.

As a solution to both of the above estimation problems (OLS mismatch and null flows), Santos and Tenreyro (2006) proposed the Poisson pseudo-maximum-likelihood (PPML) estimator, which is often used for counting data. According to classical economic theory, if two variables are related by a constant elasticity model, such as in the gravity model, the function can be interpreted as the conditional expectation of the value of the explanatory variable for a given level of the explanatory variable. Obtaining an effective parameter estimate is possible in this case by using the Poisson pseudo-maximum-likelihood (PPML) estimator. The authors argue that for this estimator, the data do not need to follow a Poisson distribution, nor does the response variable need to be an integer for the Poisson likelihood-based estimator to be consistent. Moreover, the use of the estimator eliminates the problem of zero flows (Westerlund and Wilhelmsson, 2011).

The estimating regression of gravity model using PPML method has the following form:

$$T_{ijt} = \exp[\ln \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \ln Y_{jt} + \beta_2 \ln Y_{jt} + \gamma \ln Z_{ij} + \alpha \ln X_{ijt} + \delta D_{ij} + \nu_{ij} + \ln \epsilon_{ijt}] \quad (3)$$

It should be noted that in regression (3), the time effects, ν_t and the country-pair-specific effects η_{ij} are estimated as fixed effects, which means that some time-invariant effects cannot be estimated. In accordance with the above discussion, the estimation of all gravity models presented in the article was carried out using the PPML procedure with robust standard errors in Stata 17.

30. In the literature, there are various approaches to solving the problem of zero flows. One of them is simply removing country pairs with zero turnover from the dataset. However, this can result in the loss of information and lead to unreliable estimation results. An alternative approach is to use the original series trade flow between countries as the dependent variable. This approach faces challenges due to the large range of values, and attempts to rescale the series values usually lead to inaccurate estimation of the results. Subsequently, nonlinear can be used at least squares (Frankel and Wei, 1993), which, on the one hand, is an asymptotically correct estimator for a non-linear flow model, but on the other, may be inefficient as it ignores the problem of heteroscedasticity (Santos Silva and Tenreyro 2006).

4. Results

4.1 Descriptive statistics

The analysis encompasses 53 trade partners of African countries and China for the period 2016–2021. Two countries, Sudan and Saint Helena, were excluded from the analyzes due to substantial missing data.

Table 4 presents the summary statistics for the variables in the sample used for the analysis.

The average MTCE level in the sample was 327513 (thousands of USD) with a very large deviation of 828549 (thousands of USD), respectively. The average MTCO was 38567 (thousands of USD) and the standard deviation of the sample was 85523 (thousands of USD). Both the deviation values and the difference between the minimum and maximum MTCE and MTCO values indicate a large diversification of high technology flows/imports from China to individual African countries. Such differentiation is also observed in the case of other variables describing the volume of exports and imports from China (ALIC and ALEC).

70% of the countries surveyed have access to the sea (SEA). The variable for distance from China (DIST) shows relatively low dispersion, with the shortest distance to China being 7542 km from Egypt and the longest distance being 12640 km from Cabo Verde.

The average GDP for the countries in the sample was 44584 units, with a deviation of 85355 units. The FORCE variable had an average of 13168 units with a deviation of 19094 units, while the PROD variable had an average of 4119 units with a deviation of 4374. A significant variation is also observed in the RES variable, with a mean of 9% and the deviation of 8%. The range of values for the natural resources of African countries ranges from 0% for Mauritius and South Sudan to 47% for Congo.

Table 4. Summary statistics for variables for the sample of African countries in 2016–2021

Variable name	N	Mean	SD	Min	Max
MTCE	318	327513	838549	292	7937232
MTCO	318	38567	85523	8	926044
ALIC	318	1795552	3372563	6653	25988152
ALEC	308	1223137	3417460	8	29830576
GDP	317	44584	85355	348	474517
FORCE	318	13168	19094	66	114017
PROD	317	4119	4374	212	23658
DIST	318	10640	1464	7542	12640
RES	318	9	8	0	47
RLF	318	0.393	1.021	-2.320	2.784

MTCE - high technology manufactures: electronic and electronic; MTCO - high technology manufactures: other; ALIC - total Chinese imports; ALEC - total Chinese exports; FORCE - labour force; PROD - labour productivity; DIST - distance; RES - total natural resources rents (% of GDP); RLF - measure of the development gap

Source: own elaboration.

Due to the large differences between African countries, the ratios of MTCE and MTCO to GDP and the ratios of MTCE and MTCO to ALIC were compared (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Share of high technology goods in GDP and total exports and import of African countries in total import
Source: own elaboration

Figure 2. Comparison of indicators in 2016 and 2021 relative to the level of balanced development
Source: own elaboration

The dynamics of the MTCO indicators were high during the study period for all groups of African countries except for the WA group, which is below the balanced development line. In contrast, the dynamics of the MTCE indicator were lower, except for the NA group and, in the case of the MTCE/GDP ratio, for the SA group of countries as well (Figure 2).

4.2 Estimation results

The estimation of both the basic and extended specifications of the empirical model has been performed using a PPML with robust standard errors and with a dummy variable for group membership serving as a clustering variable. The estimation was carried out using STATA 17. The results are provided in Tables 5a and 5b. The dependent variables are the value of imports of high technology. The zero adjustment is not necessary as we take into account the level of imports and not the standard log of imports. The analysis covered 53 of China's African trading partners for the period 2016–2021. Two explanatory variables were used in the study, i.e. the value of imports from China, MTCE and MTCO (thousands of USD). Significantly more relevant variables were found in the technology transfer models via MTCE than MTCO, which is consistent with expectations, as China trades much more intensively with Africa (and the entire world) in terms of MTCE.

The overall matching of the models is high, explaining 81.2% to 88.6% of the variability of imports depending on the specification. To test the robustness of the estimation results, models were estimated using two different geographic measures, DIST and SEA. The use of the latter measure required the removal of the intercept due to the collinearity of the variables. This shows that our results for the main factors, such as GDP, FORCE, and PROD, are robust to potential modifications. A model specification test was also conducted, which showed that in the case of MTCE, all models have the correct form (Table 5a). For MTCO, there was no basis to reject the hypothesis of the appropriate functional form of the models at the 0.02 significance level (Table 5b).

In most of the analyzed comparisons, the coefficients of traditional gravity model variables, such as the GDP of an African country and the distance between China and a given African country, are economically justified and their impact on the dependent variable is statistically significant. The intensity of Chinese imports decreases with the distance to the trading partner for the MTCO variable across all groups, while it is insignificant for nearly all groups in the case of the MTCE variable. Access to the sea, represented by the SEA variable, was significant only for two groups of countries, EA and CA, in the MTCE models. As expected, it was shown that geographical proximity is an important determinant of trade flows (imports) in the case of the MTCO variable, which can be associated with lower transportation and information costs in the classical approach. In the case of the second variable, the results contradict our expectations, the need to examine the costs associated with transportation and information related to the import of MTCE. This situation can be explained by theory of Baldwin and Harrigan (2011). It indicates that along with the increasing quality of products, their costs and profitability increase. Therefore, it is more profitable for China (higher profitability) to penetrate more distant markets with its flagship high-tech products. In other words, the most efficient companies (such as Chinese high-tech companies) export high-quality products to the more distant markets. This is consistent with Melitz's (2003) findings regarding markets. He argued that companies exporting to more distant markets should be more productive and consequently charge lower prices than companies that export only to nearby markets.

The impact of GDP on MTCE is significant and negative for all groups, which appears to be contrary to expectations. In contrast, no such relationship is observed for the MTCO variable. This phenomenon can be explained by the fact that other economies (the most developed), rather than China, specialize in the MTCO category. Countries that reach a certain level of wealth (for example, as indicated by GDP) decide to purchase the MTCO from other economies that specialize in their production. On the other hand, the low level of wealth of many African countries forces them to buy high-tech products (MTCE) from China (they cannot afford a better manufacturer).

The impact of the development gap, as indicated by RLF, is negative (though not significant) for the MTCO variable, suggesting that the difference in development between an African country and China is irrelevant to the volume of MTCO imports. In the case of the MTCE variable, the value of the coefficient is statistically significant and positive, which suggests that the greater the difference in development between an African country and China, the greater the tendency to import MTCE from China.

Similar to the GDP variable, the country's natural resources (RES variable) turned out to be significant only in the model of the MTCE variable for groups of countries: NA, EA, SA and WA. Its negative value indicates that the greater the country's natural resource in relation to GDP, the lower the import of MTCE from China to these countries. These groups of countries are characterized by strong raw material ties with China, hence only for these regions the variable is significant. On the other hand, the negative relationship can be explained by the fact that these countries, which strongly base their economy on raw materials, are not interested in importing modern technologies. Chinese companies located in these regions are also focused on raw materials and do not import high-tech to their plants.

The impact of the labor force of an African country, as measured by FORCE, is positive and statistically significant for all group of the countries for both variables MTCE and MTCO. This indicates that the higher the FORCE level, the greater the import from China into the country.

The impact of the African country's productivity, as measured by PROD, is positive and statistically significant for all African countries for the MTCE and MTCO. This means that the higher the PROD, the significantly greater the imports from China.

In summary, most variables in the model behaved as expected. However, variables traditionally used in gravity models, such as GDP and DIST, were exceptions. Anomalies were observed with GDP in the case of technology transfer via MTCE (where technology transfer increased with declining economic wealth). Introducing the RFL variable, an alternative to GDP, provided better results, although they varied depending on the high-tech goods group (for MTCO, RFL remained practically insignificant, while for MTCE, the relationship was positive, confirming the anomaly observed with GDP). Meanwhile, the DIST variable exhibited different behaviors depending on the technology transfer channel (in MTCO, it behaved as expected). The introduction of the SEA variable as an alternative to DIST did not improve the significance of the results obtained. However, non-traditional variables behaved as expected: FORCE and PROD demonstrated a positive relationship between technology transfer through the two discussed channels and the increase in these variables, while the RES variable typically showed a negative relationship between technology transfer and the growth in the share of the mining sector in GDP. These results indicate that technology transfer through trade in high-tech products between China and African countries is a complex process shaped by various factors, which can have differing impacts on different technology transfer channels.

5. Conclusions

Technology transfer plays a key role in economic development, especially in the context of developing countries (e.g. Henry et al., 2009; Hoekman et al., 2005). Studies have shown that technology often flows through the imports of technological goods, which is an important channel for the diffusion of innovation (e.g. Zahonogo, 2016; Keller, 2010; Rodrik, 2018). However, different economies or regions are characterized by varying channels of technology transfer and the factors determining this transfer (e.g. Wie, 2005; Mustapha and Mendi, 2015; Park and Lippoldt, 2014). Such heterogeneity complicates both the analysis of technology transfer determinants and also the development of effective technology strategies (Hoekman et al., 2005; Shukura et al., 2021). Therefore, a discussion identifying the factors influencing technology transfer is essential to understand how a country's strategy should be built to foster this transfer.

Developing economies, such as those in Africa, rely heavily on high-tech imports from countries

Table 5a. Results of model estimation for MTCE

Regressor	Group NA	Group EA	Group CA	Group SA	Group WA	Group NA	Group EA	Group CA	Group SA	Group WA
lnDIST	-0.232	0.074*	-0.006	0.015	-0.028					
SEA						0.013	0.018*	0.016*	0.010	0.011
lnGDP	-0.737*	-0.565*	-0.551*	-0.638*	-0.675*	-0.698*	-0.575*	-0.516*	-0.628*	-0.634*
lnFORCE	0.846*	0.674*	0.656*	0.745*	0.781*	0.806*	0.681*	0.621*	0.735*	0.741*
lnPROD	0.278*	0.142*	0.247*	0.226*	0.282*	0.246*	0.236*	0.236*	0.244*	0.243*
RES	-0.077*	-0.061**	-0.032	-0.119*	-0.092*	-0.090*	-0.080*	-0.039	0.120*	-0.106*
RLF	0.518*	0.487*	0.372*	0.473*	0.454*	0.509*	0.405*	0.348*	0.445*	0.450*
Group NA	-0.032*					-0.028*				
Group EA		0.039*					0.030*			
Group CA			-0.041*					-0.043*		
Group SA				-0.023*					-0.016	
Group WA					0.014					0.006
R ²	0.881	0.886	0.883	0.881	0.880	0.881	0.885	0.884	0.881	0.881
Z	-1.34	-1.17	-1.33	-1.37	-1.42	-1.42	-1.43	-1.44	-1.47	-1.46

*p<0.05; **p<0.10

z – test statistics of the analytical form of the model source: own elaboration.

Table 5b. Results of model estimation for MTCO

Regressor	Group NA	Group EA	Group CA	Group SA	Group WA	Group NA	Group EA	Group CA	Group SA	Group WA
lnDIST	-0.156*	-0.134*	-0.142*	-0.138*	-0.186*					
SEA						-0.009	-0.003	-0.007	-0.015	-0.007
lnGDP	-0.180	-0.104	-0.053	-0.110	-0.168	-0.056	-0.031	-0.021	-0.087	-0.064
lnFORCE	0.314*	0.233*	0.180	0.238*	0.296*	0.187	0.163	0.151	0.218**	0.196
lnPROD	0.347*	0.317*	0.323*	0.322*	0.385*	0.145*	0.140*	0.142*	0.148*	0.145*
RES	-0.035	-0.050	-0.009	-0.055	-0.033	-0.061	-0.031	-0.018	-0.075	-0.060
RLF	-0.085	-0.130	-0.184**	-0.130	-0.134	-0.015	-0.029	-0.044	-0.016	-0.008
Group NA	-0.024					0.007				
Group EA		0.003					0.026*			
Group CA			-0.025					-0.022		
Group SA				-0.003					-0.034	
Group WA					-0.024					-0.005
R ²	0.816	0.816	0.816	0.816	0.817	0.812	0.813	0.812	0.814	0.812
Z	-2.40 +	-2.34 +	-2.34 +	-2.36 +	-2.42 +	-1.98	-2.13 +	-1.97	-2.03 +	-2.01

p<0.05; **p<0.10; + 0.02 < p <= 0.05

z – test statistics of the analytical form of the model source: own elaboration.

like China to drive their growth. Africa's reliance on Chinese technology is rooted in the rapidly growing trade and investment relationship between the two economies, which has both positive and negative implications for the economic development (Murphy, 2022; Large, 2021). Identifying the relevant determinants influencing technology transfer allows for appropriate management not only of relations with China, but also with other technology suppliers.

In this study, we focused on analyzing the determinants affecting technology transfer from China to Africa, understood as two categories of technology transfer. An important aspect of this study was to understand how different economic and geographical factors affect these two technology streams and how different African regions may respond differently to changes in these determinants.

The following conclusions emerge from the study. The analysis of high-tech imports from China to African countries reveals several key insights. The study's models demonstrate high explanatory power, confirming the robustness of factors like GDP, labor force (FORCE), and productivity (PROD) in influencing import levels. The distance between China and African countries decreases the intensity of imports (MTCO) but is insignificant for MTCE. Contrary to expectations, GDP negatively impacts MTCE imports, suggesting wealthier African countries prefer high-tech goods from more developed economies. Development gaps positively influence MTCE imports, indicating reliance on affordable Chinese technology. Natural resources negatively affect MTCE imports in resource-rich regions, likely due to their focus on raw materials. Overall, these findings underscore the complexity of trade dynamics and the significant role of both economic and developmental factors.

In conclusion, the study provides a nuanced understanding of the factors influencing high-tech imports from China to Africa. The findings suggest that while geographical and economic factors play a crucial role, the developmental and resource contexts of African countries also significantly influence trade patterns. The unexpected results related to GDP and natural resources highlight the complexity of international trade dynamics and the need for further research to understand the underlying mechanisms driving these relationships. Furthermore, the limited significance of variables like DIST (except for MTCO) and SEA indicates that, for some technology transfer channels, geographical conditions may not play a significant role.

The study has practical and policy implications in the following areas.

First, in the areas of trade, investment and technology policies, African governments should develop specific trade and investment policies based on different technology categories. Since various technology transfer streams respond differently to changes in determinants, it is necessary to adapt import strategies to the specific needs of the high-tech electronic and electrical and other high-tech sectors. A similar implication could be found in studies by Urata and Okabe (2010) or Heintz (2013). At the same time, Africa's geographic diversity requires the adaptation of regional policies. African countries should take into account regional differences in their technology import strategies. These adaptations were detailed discussed in Leke et al. (2018) and Kwasi Fosu (2017).

The second area of influence is strategic planning. The observed differences in responses to changes in the values of determinants, as revealed through descriptive analysis and model estimation, may have implications for strategic planning across geographical regions. A similar implication was found in Ake (2014).

Another area of influence is international cooperation and strategic partnerships with China to facilitate technology transfer. Cooperation through bilateral agreements can help overcome geographical and economic barriers, as demonstrated by Sun et al. (2017) and Brautigam (2020).

Finally, the study suggests that comparing the position of non-African economies in terms of technology imports from China can lead to corrections of ineffective strategies or the introduction of innovative tools in African countries. This highlights the role of innovation in promoting technology transfer (Moyo, 2018).

At the end of the considerations, a number of research limitations and areas for further research

should be mentioned. First, a major obstacle was the limited availability of statistical data for African countries. Therefore, two economies were excluded from the study, and for the remaining ones, the variables included in the study had to be reduced to those that were reasonably complete. It is possible that access to more detailed data would reveal additional factors influencing high-tech imports from China to Africa. Second, the study relied on specific methods, and it cannot be excluded that other methods might have yielded different results. Nonetheless, the method used seemed to the authors to be the most appropriate for this type of study. Third, this study should be repeated in subsequent years to verify the results, especially due to the war in Ukraine. It is likely that this event may have disrupted previous trends. Fourth, the study was conducted at a certain level, with high-tech goods divided into two categories. However, within each category, there are more specific types of products. It is possible that a more detailed analysis might more accurately identify the determinants affecting the import of specific technologies from China. Fifth, the study adopted a geographical division of Africa into regions, but it cannot be ruled out that the use of a different disjoint division of economies might yield different results. Finally, the analysis can be extended to include other economies (e.g. European or Asian countries) to compare their position in African technology imports from China. Such comparison could result in improvements in ineffective strategies or the introduction of innovative tools in African countries.

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